

Germplasm improvement

Genetics

Inheritance of aroma and breadthwise grain expansion in Basmati and non-Basmati rices

P. Vivekanandan and S. Giridharan, Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute (TNRRI) Aduthurai 612101, Tamil Nadu, India

Aroma is the most important criterion for distinguishing Basmati from non-Basmati rice. Minimum breadthwise grain expansion is a desirable Basmati rice quality. We studied the inheritance of aroma and breadthwise grain expansion in Basmati (Pusa Basmati 1) and non-Basmati rice varieties (TKM9, ADT37, ADT39, IR50, and Improved White Ponni).

The non-Basmatis were crossed with Pusa Basmati 1 during 1991 dry season (DS). F_1 and parents were sown during 1991 wet season (WS). F_1 plants were selfed and backcrossed ($BC_1 - F_1 \times P_1$; $BC_2 - F_1 \times P_2$). Non-Basmati varieties were again crossed with Pusa Basmati 1 to produce F_1 seed.

We grew 30 plants for each replication of P_1 , P_2 , and F_1 (two 3-m rows); 120 plants for F_2 (eight rows); and 45 plants for BC_1 and BC_2 (three rows) during 1992 DS. The trial was replicated three times. One seedling/hill was planted using a spacing of 30 cm between rows and 20 cm between plants. We evaluated 10 plants per replication in P_1 , P_2 , and F_1 ; 70 plants in F_2 ; and 30 plants in BC_1 and BC_2 . To evaluate aroma, 2 g of chopped blade from the leaf below the flag leaf of each plant was soaked in 10 ml of 1.7% KOH solution in a test tube for 10 min at 30 °C. Samples were classified as aromatic or nonaromatic by smelling.

All F_1 plants were nonaromatic, indicating that aroma was recessive (Table 1). F_2 of two crosses, ADT37/Pusa Basmati 1 and IR50/Pusa Basmati 1, segregated into 3 nonaromatic: 1 aromatic, suggesting monogenic

inheritance that was confirmed in BC_1 and BC_2 generations. Cross combinations TKM9/Pusa Basmati 1, ADT39/Pusa Basmati 1, and Improved White Ponni/Pusa Basmati 1 segregated into a 15-1 ratio for nonaromatic and aromatic in F_2 , indicating digenic inheritance that was confirmed in BC_1 and BC_2 generations.

Segregation due to monogenic or digenic recessive genes suggests that genes responsible for aroma may differ with the breeding materials used in a study.

To evaluate for inheritance of breadthwise grain expansion, 4-mo-old rough rice was hulled using a McGill sheller and milled in a Kett rice polisher. Ten randomly selected whole milled kernels were measured (mm) before and after cooking using a graduated piece of

cardboard. Milled kernels were cooked using the method of Juliano and Perez. The ratio of mean breadth of cooked rice to mean breadth of milled rice was computed as breadthwise grain expansion.

Bold-grained parents TKM9 and ADT37 recorded the least breadthwise expansion (Table 2). The mean value of F_1 toward minimum breadthwise expansion indicated its dominance over maximum breadthwise expansion. BC_1 with the better parent produced less breadthwise expansion than BC_2 , with the other parent.

Additive, dominance, and dominance \times dominance effects were significant (Table 2). The h and l effects had opposite signs, revealing the presence of duplicate gene action. Effective factors ranged from 1 to 18. Because additive

Table 1. Chi-square test for inheritance of aroma, TRRI, Aduthurai, India.

Designation	Generation	Plants (no.)			Expected ratio of nonaromatic to aromatic	χ^2	Probability
		Tested	Nonaromatic	Aromatic			
TKM9		30	30	-	1:0		
ADT37		30	30	-	1:0		
ADT39		30	30	-	1:0		
IR50		30	30	-	1:0		
Improved White Ponni		30	30	-	1:0		
Pusa Basmati 1		30	-	30	0:1		
TKM9/Pusa Basmati 1	F_1	30	30	-	1:0		
	F_2	210	193	17	15:1	1.22	0.20-0.30
	BC_1	90	90	-	1:0		
	BC_2	90	63	27	3:1	1.20	0.20-0.30
ADT37/Pusa Basmati 1	F_1	30	30	-	1:0		
	F_2	210	164	46	3:1	1.07	0.30-0.50
	BC_1	90	90	-	1:0		
	BC_2	90	48	42	1:1	0.40	0.50-0.70
ADT39/Pusa Basmati 1	F_1	30	30	-	1:0		
	F_2	210	195	15	15:1	0.29	0.50-0.70
	BC_1	90	90	-	1:0		
	BC_2	90	65	25	3:1	0.37	0.50-0.70
IR50/Pusa Basmati 1	F_1	30	30	-	1:0		
	F_2	210	163	47	3:1	0.77	0.30-0.50
	BC_1	90	90	-	1:0		
	BC_2	90	50	40	1:1	1.12	0.20-0.30
Improved White Ponni/Pusa Basmati 1	F_1	30	30	-	1:0		
	F_2	210	194	16	15:1	0.67	0.30-0.50
	BC_1	90	90	-	1:0		
	BC_2	90	67	23	3:1	0.02	0.80-0.90

Table 2. Mean values of breadthwise grain expansion for six generations and estimates of gene effects.^a TRRI, Aduthurai, India.

	TKM9/Pusa Basmati 1	ADT37/Pusa Basmati 1	ADT39/Pusa Basmati 1	IR50/Pusa Basmati 1	Improved White Ponni/Pusa Basmati 1
<i>Generation</i>					
P ₁	1.34 ± 0.007	1.38 ± 0.001	1.50 ± 0.005	1.57 ± 0.009	1.53 ± 0.010
P ₂	1.64 ± 0.012	1.69 ± 0.012	1.65 ± 0.013	1.64 ± 0.011	1.62 ± 0.012
P ₁	1.47 ± 0.009	1.43 ± 0.012	1.51 ± 0.010	1.60 ± 0.012	1.61 ± 0.009
P ₂	1.41 ± 0.007	1.48 ± 0.006	1.53 ± 0.007	1.59 ± 0.008	1.55 ± 0.007
BC ₁	1.41 ± 0.012	1.43 ± 0.008	1.49 ± 0.010	1.55 ± 0.008	1.54 ± 0.011
BC ₂	1.61 ± 0.013	1.61 ± 0.009	1.54 ± 0.010	1.63 ± 0.010	1.57 ± 0.009
<i>Parameter</i>					
m	1.08* ± 0.05	1.37* ± 0.04	1.62* ± 0.04	1.63* ± 0.04	1.56* ± 0.04
d	-0.15* ± 0.01	-0.15* ± 0.01	-0.08* ± 0.01	-0.03* ± 0.01	-0.05* ± 0.01
h	0.92* ± 0.12	0.35* ± 0.09	-0.27* ± 0.10	-0.11 ± 0.10	-0.10 ± 0.10
i	0.41* ± 0.04	0.16* ± 0.03	-0.04 ± 0.02	-0.02 ± 0.04	0.01 ± 0.04
j	-0.10* ± 0.04	-0.05 ± 0.03	0.03 ± 0.03	-0.08* ± 0.03	-0.02 ± 0.03
l	-0.53* ± 0.08	-0.30* ± 0.06	0.15* ± 0.07	0.09 ± 0.07	0.14* ± 0.07
<i>Effective factors</i>					
(d ²)/D	—	3.8	0.9	0.1	0.3
(h ²)/H	14.8	17.5	4.6	—	0.6

^a* = significant at the 5% level.

gene action is present, the pedigree breeding method is recommended. Dominance and epistatic interactions were also seen; selection in later

generations with one or two cycles of intermating selected segregants will result in lessening breadthwise grain expansion. ■

Inheritance of aroma in two rice crosses

S. Geetha, Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute, Aduthurai 612101, Tamil Nadu, India

Two nonscented varieties, ADT38 and ADT39, were crossed with a scented variety, Badshabhog, to study the inheritance of aroma in rice. The parents, F₁, and F₂ were grown in Nov 1992. For each cross, 2 g of leaf blades from 15 randomly selected parent and F₁ plants and 200 F₂ plants were soaked in

10 ml of 1.7% KOH solution in test tubes and evaluated for scent after 10 min by smelling the contents.

All F₁ plants were nonaromatic, indicating the recessive nature of the gene controlling aroma (see table). A 15 nonaromatic: 1 aromatic segregation occurred for F₂ plants in both crosses, suggesting that two recessive genes control aroma in Badshabhog. Pedigree breeding with a larger population for F₂ selection is suggested for introducing scent into nonscented varieties. ■

Behavior of F₁ and F₂ populations with regard to inheritance of aroma.

Cross	Plants (no.)			c ²	P
	Total	Nonaromatic	Aromatic		
<i>F₁</i>					
ADT38/Badshabhog	15	15	—	—	—
ADT39/Badshabhog	15	15	—	—	—
<i>F₂</i>					
ADT38/Badshabhog	200	189	11	0.19	0.50-0.75
ADT39/Badshabhog	200	190	10	0.53	0.25-0.50

Breeding methods

Evaluation of rice cytoplasmic male sterile lines for floral traits influencing outcrossing

K. V. Seetharamaiah, R. S. Kulkarni, M. Mahadevappa, and T. G. Prasad, Genetics and Plant Breeding Department, GKVK University of Agricultural Sciences, Bangalore 560065, India

The success of hybrid rice technology depends as much on developing stable male sterility and restoration systems as on the amount of seed set on cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines by natural outcrossing. Rice is an autogamous crop; high outcrossing does not generally occur. Considerable outcrossing, however, has been reported in some wild species as a function of floral structure and biology. Environmental variation may influence the expression of these traits.

We evaluated 15 CMS lines for nine floral traits influencing outcrossing under two irrigated environments: 1991 dry season (DS) and 1991 wet season (WS). Five spikelets were randomly selected from the main panicle in each CMS line to record anther and stigma traits using stage and ocular micrometers. Anthesis duration was recorded as the time

IRRN REMINDER

Routine research. Reports of screening trials of varieties, fertilizer, cropping methods, and other routine observations using standard methodologies to establish local recommendations are not ordinarily accepted. Examples are single-season, single-trial field experiments. Field trials should be repeated across more than one season, in multiple seasons, or in more than one location as appropriate. All experiments should include replications and an internationally known check or control treatment.